

Continuing pharmacy education and training in Libya

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Lifelong learning is becoming part of the philosophy of professional education. Continuing medical education is a responsibility of all personal who are responsible for the delivery of components of the health care delivery system. Continuing education is becoming increasingly obvious for medical universities, hospitals and health care providers. Pharmacists who are practice in a community pharmacy and hospital, and who are participating in residency recognize that the traditional role of the pharmacist is undergoing change. Over the last decades, a host of new services have been identified as a function of the pharmacist [1]. A review of these services reveled a personal commitment to continuing education. It is the absolute need to develop a level of competence that will improve patient care. In Libya, pharmacists working in the community practice setting are pharmacists with diploma of pharmacy or with Bachelor of Pharmaceutical sciences, Master of Science and doctor of pharmacy (Pharm D). The main objective is that the graduates possess the knowledge and skills needed to perform optimally to man the pharmaceutical services [1, 2]. Patient's expectations from the pharmacists are that the medicine should be effective, safe and affordable. Other expectations from Libyan pharmacists would be to dispense the drugs according to the rules with right advice on how and when the medicines should be used, and what to do in the case of adverse drug reactions and the provision of advice on common illnesses. Nevertheless, it is an undeniable fact that the pharmacist has failed to provide all these patient oriented services [3]. It should be noted that the quality of pharmacy education and training can be improved through certain process of accreditation.

The need for the continuing education of pharmacists was highlighted during the 1950s. The concept of continuing education has also been existed among scholars but recent time has it evolved conspicuously as an integral part of the education process. The concept of continuing education becomes one of re-enforcement of primary objective in the life of a professional person. There are those who feel that continuing education should be a fringe benefit of employment. But others who feel that mandatory continuing education should be essential and indispensable while the opposition is equally adamant. There is a great deal of justification for supporting the position that continuing education be provided as a fringe benefit of employment. In Libya, pharmacy education and training is relatively new but become more required. However, fifty years ago, there was no education of pharmacy or training in Libya. The oldest faculty of pharmacy is located in Tripoli (university of Tripoli, established in 1975) which considered the mother of pharmacy education, training and practice in Libya [3]. Now, there are about ten public faculties and several private faculties offering pharmacy

education at the bachelor's levels. Pharmacy education in Libya is regulated by Ministry of Higher Education. Libyan Pharmacy Union is responsible for registration of persons fulfilling the prescribed eligibility criteria and issuing a license permitting them to practice. Thereafter, services and identified functions of pharmacist were hosted in Libya by both governmental and non-governmental organizations to provide different courses in continuing pharmacy education for community and hospital pharmacists. In addition, postgraduate studies leading to a professional degree in pharmacology and pharmaceuticals (Master of Science) were established in University of Tripoli more than 20 years [2]. Other attempts as pharmacy Libyan board in clinical pharmacy (pediatrics, oncology and internal medicine) have not been fully successful done due certain reasons such as lack of teaching and supervising staff in university hospitals [2]. Libyan Pharmaceutical association and society have organized some professional pharmacy courses for community and hospital pharmacists toward a better patient care and practice including clinical pharmacy, drug quality control and drug good storage. In hospitals, education and training division supervises a general staff educational meeting of a broad educational interest to all members of the staff of the pharmacy. Some examples of the type of continuing educational activities which may be desirable for a group of pharmacists are drug information conference, pharmacy clinical conference and professional health conference, and pharmacist therapeutic committee.

In conclusion, till now, pharmacy education in Libya has not succeeded in creating pharmacist as a member of healthcare team that fails to figure in National Health Policy, and this proves that the pharmacy education programs need modification regarding curriculum. There is a need for all out efforts from all stakeholders to promote pharmacy practice and build up public perception of pharmacist as in many of the developed countries.

Conflict of interest: The author declares absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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